

Role of Indonesian Military in Forest and Land Fire Fighting In Riau Province during Pandemic

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Abstract: *The role of the Indonesian Military (TNI) in disaster management is the implementation of the TNI main task, namely Military Operations Other Than War (OMSP) which is carried out by helping to cope with natural disasters, evacuation, and providing humanitarian assistance and efforts to reduce losses due to natural disasters (forest and land fires) with the aim of creating sense of security in society. The purpose of this study was to examine the role of the TNI-AD Korem 031/Wira Bima (Indonesian National Army in Military Resort Command 031/Wira Bima) in overcoming forest and land fires in the Riau Province to create a sense of security from the dangers of fire and the thick smoke it causes. The research method used is qualitative research, with a qualitative descriptive design through data collection and analysis based on information obtained during virtual work activities in the country. Primary data was obtained from interviews and FGD (Focus Group Discussion) with the informant Commander of Korem 031/Wira Bima and secondary data was obtained through searching books and research journals that already existed. The study concluded that the role of the TNI-AD Korem 031/Wira Bima was quite notable with the results of a significant reduction in forest and land fires, especially 9,717.80 hectares of fires in 2019 decrease to 1,412.08 hectares in 2021 during pandemic, and the sky turned blue.*

Keywords: *Forest Fires, Indonesian Military, Land Fires, Pandemic Covid-19, Role*

I. INTRODUCTION

National Security (Kamnas) can be interpreted either as a condition or as a function. If interpreted as a function, national security means producing and creating a sense of security in a broad sense, which includes a sense of comfort, peace, tranquility and order. Conditions and a sense of security are basic human needs (Darmono, 2010). Indonesian defense not only adheres to the concept of traditional/territorial security with an emphasis on national defense on the nature of military threats and territorial sovereignty, but also on human security from all forms of threats (Darma, 2019). And one form of non-military threat that can disrupt the lives and security of people in Riau Province is forest fires, both intentional and unintentional fires.

Role is defined as an activity that is played by someone who has a position or social status in the organization. Roles can also be described as social relations in terms of actors who play a role according to what is in accordance with the culture and rules that exist in a place, another understanding is explained that role theory is a theory which is a combination of theory, orientation, and various fields of science (Brink & Wood in

Widyaningrum 2020). Kahn *et al.*, (in Ahmad and Taylor, 2009) also introduced role theory to the organizational behavior literature, suggesting that an organizational environment can influence everyone's expectations about their attitudes and actions. These expectations include norms or pressures to act in certain ways. Each of them will receive the message, interpret it, and respond in various ways. According to Sukanto (2001) the role can be divided into three parts, namely an active role, a passive role and a participatory role.

The role played by the Regional Government of Riau Province so far has not gone unnoticed regarding the haze caused by forest fires. This problem is also in the spotlight for neighboring countries, especially countries whose geographical location is not far from Riau Province. These cross-geographical and cross-country losses have occurred continuously since 1998 and have caused social, economic and environmental losses. The capability of the Riau Provincial government is highly demanded in controlling forest and land fires. A capability is a form of ability that must be possessed by the central and regional governments to face the challenges and problems that occur in the dynamics and changes. The continuous fires indicate that the Riau Provincial Government is not able to control forest fires, as can be seen from its effect, namely the smog. This shows that a good collaboration is needed to control forest and land fires that cause smog across agencies, especially the Indonesian National Army (TNI) (Meiwanda, 2016).

The challenges during the COVID-19 pandemic provide us with an unprecedented opportunity for us to change direction and a new vision for the health of the planet earth to incorporate the protection and restoration of tropical forests into its policies. Stopping and reversing tropical deforestation is an essential part of any strategy to reduce the likelihood of future pandemics, and to reorganize the relationship between humans and nature (Interfaith Prakasa for Tropical Forests, 2020).

The role of the TNI-AD Korem 031/ Wira Bima in the process of handling forest and land fires in Riau Province is the implementation of the TNI's main duties in accordance with Article 7 of Law No. 34 of 2004 concerning the TNI's main tasks, namely Military Operations Other than War (OMSP). This role is very significant in reducing forest and land fires in the Riau region so that there is a significant reduction in the area of forest and land fires, the role played before, during and after the fire. The condition of Riau Province has a high level of vulnerability to fires because 54% of Riau's area consists of peatlands that are easy to burn and difficult to extinguish, this is the attention of researchers to see the role that has been carried out by Korem 031/Wira Bima (Fauzi & Angga Nurdin R, 2014).

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. National Security

According to Juwono Sudarsono, a comprehensive national security system is based on four ideal government functions, as follows: (1) National Defense is the function of the State government in dealing with threats from abroad to uphold national sovereignty, safety, honor and integrity of the Republic of Indonesia; (2) State Security, namely the function of the State government in dealing with domestic threats. (3) Public Security, namely the function of the State government in maintaining and restoring safety, security, and public order through law enforcement, protection, shelter, and public service; (4) Human Security, namely the function of the State government to uphold the basic rights of citizens. From the basic concept of security, it is explained that security is not only oriented to state security but also public security and human security or individual security against all forms of threats, both military and non-military. Non-military threats that continue to increase are threats caused by disasters both caused by nature and by human actions (Mukhtar, 2017).

There is an increasing trend in the incidence of global natural disasters, also in the Southeast Asia region which can be seen statistically, and Indonesia, in particular is one of the regions with high risk and exposure to disasters. Indonesia, which is located on the "ring of fire" geographically and is a confluence of 3 tectonic plates, in the form of an archipelago, is in a tropical area, and the phenomenon of climate change, makes Indonesia must be aware of the potential for natural disasters that can occur at any time. *The United*

Nations Secretariat for International Strategy for Disaster Reduction (UNISDR) declared Indonesia as the 5th country with the highest natural disaster incidence in the world from 2005 to 2014. Indonesia also shows a tendency for escalation and the intensity of natural disasters to increase every year as shown by natural disasters data, which can be seen in Figure 1.

Fig 1. the number of natural disasters in Indonesia 2000-2019.

Source: BNPB

National security with an increase in natural disasters is a real threat to the life and safety of the Indonesian nation. In addition, natural disasters also affect the socio-economic life of the community. The increase in natural disasters that continues to rise can be seen in Figure 1, where this is often not balanced with the preparedness and capability of the government and the community in overcoming them (Darma Agung, 2019).

2.2. Disaster Risk in Riau Province

Natural disasters that occur in Riau Province still tend to be high year after year, especially the incidence of land and forest fires, although in the last two years they have decreased quite drastically. The total area of Riau Province is 111,228.65 square kilometers (the area after the expansion of the Riau Islands Province) which consists of islands and the sea. Its existence stretches from the slopes of Bukit Barisan to the North Natuna Sea, geologically it is located in the back arc basin of the mountains with the dominance of peatlands in most of the eastern region of Riau Province. The existence of extensive peatlands and forests causes Riau Province to often experience forest and land fires.

This disaster resulted in a decrease of air quality in Riau Province, that it had an impact on health and also disrupted flights. In addition, smoke from forest and land fires in Riau Province has reached neighbouring countries, Singapore and Malaysia. Based on the 2020 Indonesian Disaster Risk Index (IRBI), Riau Province has a high-risk index of 147.27 as shown in figure 2. (BNPB, 2020).

Fig 2. Graph of the Riau Province Disaster Risk Index in 2015-2020

Source: BNPB

Forest and land fires can occur both inside and outside forest areas, on mineral soils and peat. The difficulty is quite high in overcoming forest fires that occur in peatland areas caused by fires that can spread through the aboveground

biomass and in the peat layer below the surface, this is because of the smoldering process in peatlands is difficult to detect visually. During the long dry season, dry peat conditions due to land clearing and canals/ditches can cause peatlands to burn easily (Yusuf et al., 2019).

Riau Province has peat forest land formed by the accumulation of organic matter on land that tends to be inundated with an area of about 4.9 million hectares or about 54.44% of Riau Province's land area, consisting of freshwater peat swamp and tidal peat swamp, which most of them are located in the eastern part, and this area is a strong point for fires to occur. Low-lying areas will be vulnerable to floods and inundation, as has been happening regularly. The existence of abandoned land has created critical land in several parts of Riau Province. The clearing of secondary forests for agricultural land and community gardens has led to the formation of critical lands because these cultivated lands are not properly maintained and are abandoned. The abandoned land turns into shrubs and weeds, this also becomes vulnerable to fires. The distribution of peatlands and critical lands that are prone to fires has a high-grade level in all districts and cities in Riau Province as shown in table 1.

Table 1. Class Levels of Forest and Land Fire Hazards

No	Regency/City	Risk Area (Ha)			
		Low	Moderate	High	Total
A	Regency				
1	Bengkalis	57.315	171.591	616.675	845.581
2	Indragiri Hilir	157.928	314.147	851.696	1.322.271
3	Indragiri Hulu	116.878	389.537	320.388	826.803
4.	Kampar	277.872	377.525	363.014	1.018.411
5	Kepulauan Meranti	427.754	120.907	197.248	360.909
6	Kuantan Singingi	94.124	288.313	231.903	554.340
7	Pelalawan	37.240	312.506	936.606	1.306.352
8.	Rokan Hilir	24.547	229.779	677.601	931.927
9.	Rokan Hulu	132.932	446.022	186.980	765.934
10	Siak	32.756	242.593	505.881	781.230
B	City				
1	Kota Dumai	12.345	32.386	153.259	197.990
2.	Kota Pekanbaru	38.602	15.331	9.904	63.837
	Riau Province	1.045.293	2.879.637	5.051.155	8.976.085

Source: BPBD Riau Province

2.3. Civil-Military Cooperation

In obedience to TNI Law Number 34 Article 7 Paragraph 2, the main task of The TNI as referred to in paragraph 1 (upholding state sovereignty, defending the territorial integrity of the Unitary State of the Republic of Indonesia based on Pancasila and the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, and protecting the entire nation and the entire homeland of Indonesia from threats and disturbances to the integrity of the nation and state) is carried out with Military Operations Other than War (OMSP) and in number 12 letter *b* it reads that

the task of OMSP is carried out by helping to cope with the consequences of natural disasters, evacuation, and providing humanitarian assistance. From the above understanding, cooperation between civilians and the military is crucial in every disaster (TNI Law Number 34).

Civil and military cooperation is a very important thing for a nation. This is because it has a major influence on the nation's national security. National resilience itself is a matter of endurance (strong), determination, and fortitude in the context of awareness. Or more clearly, it can be concluded that national resilience has an understanding of resilience (strong), determination, and fortitude from unity in fighting for the national interest of a nation that has become a state. The word civil is an understanding that relates to society, or citizens in general. While the military is the definition concerned with armed force. Concretely, the word civilian in Indonesia means the whole community, while the word military means the Indonesian National Army (TNI), which is an organization that is an armed force which must protect the sovereignty of the Republic of Indonesia. Because civilians mean the community, the military is part of the community, so civil-military cooperation is something that must continue to be worked on in the various problems that exist, in this case concerning disaster problems, especially forest and land fire disasters in the Riau Province (Sri Sundari, 2021). Thus, every effort related to disaster management, especially in overcoming forest and land fires in Riau Province, not only involves government agencies (civil) but also involves military agencies. In almost all disasters that occur the role of the TNI in disasters is seen to be very dominant. This study is intended to discuss the role played by the TNI-AD (Korem 031/Wira Bima) in the management of land and forest fires, which is focused on the Riau Province as an area that has a high level of disaster vulnerability, especially forest and land fires.

Fig 3. geographical location of riau province as research location.

Source: RPJMD Riau Province Year 2019-2024

III. RESEARCH METHODS

This research is qualitative. Qualitative research is a method used to explore and understand the perceived meanings of social or humanitarian problems of several individuals or groups of people (Creswell, 2010). In this case, qualitative research was chosen to explore and unravel the theme "The Role of TNI-AD in Combating Forest and Land Fires in Riau Province". The research design used is descriptive, namely through data collection and analysis in qualitative methods supported by the results of assessments based on information obtained during domestic work lectures which are carried out virtually (exposure to material from informant and answers in question and answer sessions) and literature studies using secondary data. The information obtained will then be processed into a review in the discussion of this research.

The time of the research was carried out for 6 days from February 7th-12nd, 2022. The location of the research was carried out in Riau Province, especially the TNI-AD Korem 031/Wira Bima agency. Primary data was obtained from the results of interviews and FGD (*Focus Group Discussion*) with informant (Korem

Commander 031/Wira Bima) and secondary data was obtained through searching existing books and research journals. The object of this research is the role of TNI-AD Korem 031/Wira Bima in handling forest and land fires in Riau Province. The data analysis technique in this study was started based on data collection techniques and data analysis techniques through interviews and FGDs followed by data condensation intending to select data and focus on the validity of the data, presenting data using qualitative data in narrative form and drawing conclusions. (Miles *et al.*, 2014).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Role Theory

Role means something that is played or carried out. Role is defined as an activity that is played or played by someone who has a position or social status in the organization (Indonesian Ministry of Education, 2014). Role theory is a theory which is a combination of theory, orientation, and various fields of science. Apart from psychology, role theory originates from sociology and anthropology (Brink & Wood, 1994 in Widyaningrum 2020). In the three fields of science, the term "role" was born from the world of drama or theatre. In drama/theatre, an actor must play a certain individual and in his role as a character, he is meant to do something according to his choice. The position of the actor in the theatre/drama is then equated with one's position in community life.

Linton (in Hutami, 2011), an anthropologist, has developed a role theory. Role theory is described as social relations in terms of actors who act according to what is in conformity with the culture and customs that exist in a place. Based on this theory, role ideals are shared understandings that lead characters to behave and act in their daily lives. According to this theory, individuals who have certain roles, for example teachers, students, police, military, etc., are desired so that someone or individuals who take on these roles can act according to the roles they have. Why would someone teach students in a school? Because he is a teacher. So because someone is a teacher, he is obliged to teach at school or at home and this behavior is determined by his social role.

Broadly speaking, roles can be described as expectations about an appropriate attitude towards their job position, for example as a leader, subordinate, etc. There are two types of expected behavior in duties and responsibilities, namely *role perception* and *role expectation*. *Role perception* is the perception that someone wants about how that person behaves, and *role expectation* is the way others understand and accept someone's attitudes and behavior under certain conditions. In an organization (civil and military and society), the role played by each individual will form a pattern in terms of self-identity and people's ability to work. So, an organization, both government and military as well as society must ensure that roles are clearly defined (Syahri, 2018).

The role according to Sukanto (2021) can be divided into three types: 1. Active role states that the actions taken by a person or group in the organization are wholly active, the contribution can be measured or seen by their participation, as well as their presence in running the organization. 2. The participatory role can be interpreted as the role performed in an organization at a certain time in fulfilment of the required needs. 3. Passive roles can be interpreted as roles that are not performed by a person/group in the organization or society, thus the roles performed are symbolic under certain conditions. From the description above, it can be concluded that the role played by the TNI AD Korem 031/Wirabima is an active and participatory role. The roles performed by Korem 031/Wira Bima are the implementation of existing laws so that in every disaster event, in this case forest and land fires, Korem 031/Wira Bima is always present in keeping with the expectations of the community and local government to make Riau's sky clear of smoke.

4.2. Active Role of TNI

TNI or the Indonesian National Armed Forces are warrior soldiers and people's soldiers who come from the people and fight for the State and people who have been specially trained and prepared to carry out the

duties of the state and nation and have the duty and responsibility to maintain national defense and security (Chalim & Farhan, 2015). The role and position of the TNI are enshrined in Law Number 34 of 2004. Law Number 34 of 2004 explains that the TNI acts as a state instrument in the defense sector that carries out its duties and responsibilities based on state political policies and decisions. The TNI has a function as a deterrent to every form of military and non-military threats as well as hybrid threats, both external and internal threats that threaten sovereignty, territorial integrity, and national safety. In carrying out the function of the TNI as a means of national defense, the TNI is the main component of the national defense system.

4.3. The active and participatory role of Korem 031/Wira Bima

At the end of 2019, the *World Meteorological Organization* (WMO) stated that the earth was in its hottest condition in history. This is thought to be due to high levels of greenhouse gases which are the main cause of global warming. In 2017, the CO₂ concentration in the atmosphere was recorded at 405.6 ppm. The concentration of CO₂ continues to increase which is followed by an increase in the earth's temperature. Indonesia's problems related to climate change and environmental degradation are also not small. On land, the problem of deforestation is still common. In 2019 Indonesia experienced a fairly large forest fire disaster. From the results of Greenpeace analysis, 3,403,000 HA of land was burned between 2015 and 2018 in Indonesia (Suryani, 2020).

Restrictions on human activities during the Covid-19 pandemic and the cessation of various economic activities, including some industrial sectors, have contributed to the reduction of global emissions. The Center for Energy and Clean Air Research (CREA) released that the world's CO₂ emissions were recorded to have decreased by 17% due to the Covid-19 quarantine implemented in various countries. Nearly half (43%) of global emission reductions during the peak of lockdowns came from the transportation and industrial sectors, particularly motor vehicles and commercial manufacturing plants. When the urban environment tends to improve, it is different in tropical forest areas. Environmental organizations report increased deforestation amid lockdowns.

In minimizing the destruction and burning of forests and land, the involvement of the TNI has an important role. The role of the TNI-AD Korem 031/ Wira Bima in forest and land fires in the Riau Province is carried out at the pre-disaster stage, during the disaster, and after the fire disaster. In the pre-disaster (fire) stage, the Korem 031/Wira Bima continues to deliver an early warning system together with local government officials, especially during the dry season, because during the dry season forest fires are more common. The warning is carried out through socialization activities prone to forest and land fires and the prohibition of burning land. Early warning in Riau was formally implemented through the establishment of an emergency alert status by the Governor of Riau who later formed the Karhutla Task Force (Satgas). The position of risk reduction in the pre-disaster period includes prevention, mitigation, and preparedness (Badri et al., 2018).

The pattern of early warning and prevention carried out by the TNI-AD Korem 031/Wira Bima through several activities including carrying out routine daily patrols either on foot, on the motorbike, or by using a patrol car. Aggressive patrols are carried out when there is a high level of vulnerability to forest and land fires. At certain times, joint patrols can also be carried out involving other agencies such as BPBD, POLRI, Manggala Agni, and others. Personnel carries out routine daily outreach activities that are held at strong points of fires with the aim of changing the mindset of the community, socialization is also carried out with religious activities during Friday prayers and church services as well as making leaflets/briefings aimed at inviting people not to burn land and Forest. The TNI-AD also carried out real work in the form of opening demonstration plots such as plantations by not burning, coordinating with local regional officials and existing plantation companies, and constructing canals and reservoirs at fire and forest fire-prone points in collaboration with companies and local governments, constructing wells. drill for areas prone to forest and land fires. In addition, personnel also stay and eat at community homes with the result that a close relationship is established between the community and the task force personnel.

The disaster (fire) stage is where after the information is received, the first activity carried out by Korem 031/Wira Bima is emergency response. Information received from the personnel of Korem 031 Wira Bima in the field must be detailed and adjusted to the level of threat and characteristics of the forest and land burned with the aim that the tools and number of personnel needed can be prepared, and the information must be disseminated quickly to government institutions, agencies, and organizations. institutions, and communities. That appropriate actions can be taken, either evacuating or rescuing property/assets and preventing further damage. Notifications can be distributed through radio, television, and written mass media (internet) in the form of a yellow sassy application, telephone, and mobile phone. During this emergency period, the role of Korem 031/Wira Bima took several steps in the form of a total extinguishment using extinguishing equipment that had been prepared at the location of strong hotspots or bringing in equipment from higher-level units, personnel movement could be carried out on foot or by vehicle or with air mobilization. If the extinguishing is not successful, TNI-AD personnel will report the fire situation to the Dansatgas Karhutla to increase troop strength so that *water booms* from the Air Task Force and the Air Task Force will coordinate with the Central Task Force then TMC can be carried out according to weather conditions at the Karhutla location.

The general objective of emergency response is to ensure the safety of as many victims as possible and to ensure that the health of the people affected by the disaster is maintained and in this case by the airborne police due to the thick haze. Provide adequate basic needs as quickly as possible for all population groups, with special attention to those most in need, namely the most vulnerable groups in terms of age, sex, and physical condition. In the case of displacement, the goal is to find long-lasting solutions as quickly as possible to find a suitable place (Purnama, 2017). In the fire and forest fires disaster during the emergency response, there were rarely any fatalities, more of the effects of thick smoke that caused ARI and lung disease. There are also not many people who have evacuated, usually the affected people are quite far from the fires, so there is no need for places for temporary shelter as explained by the commander of Korem 031/Wira Bima.

In the Post-Disaster (fire) we are still guided by the Regulation of the Head of the National Disaster Management Agency Number 17 of 2010 in carrying out activities with the basic principles of post-disaster rehabilitation and reconstruction including: (1) It is the responsibility of the Regional Government and the Government; (2) Build *back better* which is integrated with the concept of disaster risk reduction in the form of allocating funds of at least 10% of the rehabilitation and reconstruction funds; (3) Prioritizing the interests of vulnerable groups such as the elderly, women, children and people with disabilities; (4) Optimizing regional resources; (5) Leading to the achievement of community independence, sustainability of programs and activities as well as the realization of good governance; and (6) Prioritizing justice and gender equality. Korem 031/Wira Bima in carrying out post-fire disaster activities adhere to the guidelines mentioned above, especially on point one where the assistance provided by Korem 031 personnel is part of the duties and responsibilities of the central government as the implementation of the TNI Law number 34 of 2004 and point three, namely prioritizing help to vulnerable groups. In the fire disaster, the role of the TNI-AD Korem 031/Wira Bima in the post-disaster stage is not too broad because the forest and land fires are mostly carried out by human activities so that when the fire is completely extinguished, the police will follow up with installation actions. *police line* and stakes to trace and ascertain the perpetrators of the arson.

The active and participatory role carried out by TNI-AD personnel Korem 031/Wira Bima during the Covid-19 pandemic as well as good cooperation with the Riau Provincial government and other institutions resulted in very encouraging results in reducing the occurrence of forest and land fires so that in the last 2 years during the 2019-2021 pandemic, we can see Riau's sky turning blue, which means thick smoke from fires is not found in large numbers, this can be seen in Figure 4.

Fig 4. graph of forest and land fires for 2019-2022. Source: Korem 031/Wira Bima

Restrictions on human activities during the Covid-19 pandemic and the decline in economic, social, industrial, and other activities, so this has an impact on increasing community activities in the area to use forests as a place to earn a living, this is in line with what was conveyed by environmental organizations that reported increased deforestation amidst the lockdown or Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB). The Covid-19 pandemic has also had various impacts on the global environment. The positive impact is marked by a reduction in greenhouse gas emissions, improved water and air quality in urban areas, and an increase in biodiversity. But on the other hand, negative impacts are felt especially in the waste and forestry sectors which are marked by increased deforestation in the world and also in Indonesia, especially Riau Province (Suryani, 2020). This is in accordance with data which shows that during the Covid-19 pandemic there has been an increase in palm oil plantation land (deforestation) carried out by the community, which is around 1,762,163 hectares in 2020, compared to 2019 of around 1,733,959 hectares so that there is an increase in the plantation area. Palm oil palm plantations carried out by the community are around 28,204 hectares within 1 year of the pandemic (BPS Riau, 2020). This increase in land use is not accompanied by an increase in smoke in the Riau sky caused by land management patterns whose concepts have changed thanks to the education provided by Korem 031/Wira Bima and other agencies involved.

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4.4. The Less Optimal Role of Korem 031/Wira Bima

The role of Korem 031/Wira Bima in carrying out its duties also has its own challenges, especially during the Covid-19 pandemic, so this has become a separate evaluation material for Korem 031 and its staff. In these conditions, the challenge faced by Korem 031/Wira Bima personnel during the Covid-19 pandemic was the lack of personnel in the field due to the division of personnel on duty in the field where some were involved in other activities such as maintaining the flow of community movements in the PSBB programmed by the government in addition to the lack of availability. Equipment that is owned to be able to reach areas experiencing fires in the emergency stage, this is also of course greatly influenced by the government's refocusing of the budget for Covid-19 mitigation. Thus, difficulties are encountered in making canals and reservoirs, heavy equipment in fire fighting is owned by the local government and requires coordination when using it. That it is a bit hampered when dealing with fires due to a rather long bureaucratic chain.

The problems mentioned above are in line with the statement by the Director-General of Climate Change Control that the challenges faced in handling forest and land fires during the Covid-19 pandemic were caused by the government's program, namely the PSBB, to such an extent that field activities were not easy to carry out due to limited mobility. However, prevention efforts remain the main priority in Karhutla in 2020. The same thing was conveyed by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK) that the strategies for preventing forest and land fires are: Climate Analysis and steps through Weather Modification Technology, Operational Control through Field Command Post, Law enforcement, Masyarakat Peduli Api (Fire Care Community), Integrated Task Force and *Landscape* management (through training on land clearing without burning, and controlling peat). The role that is less than optimal due to this pandemic is actually a challenge in itself that can be solved with determination and hard work from the personnel of Korem 031/Wira Bima (<http://ditjenppi>).

V. CONCLUSION

The problem of deforestation is still happening, this can be seen from the Greenpeace report that there were fires in Indonesia from 2015 to 2018 covering an area of 3,403,000 hectares. This was exacerbated during the Covid-19 pandemic where people who experienced large-scale social restrictions (PSBB) to meet their economic needs used forests as a source of economic activity.

The active and participatory role of the TNI-AD Korem 031/Wira Bima in carrying out the TNI's main tasks (OMSP) is very important in tackling forest and land fires in Riau Province, thanks to the participation of Korem 031/Wira Bima and cooperation with other agencies thus forest and land fires in the Riau region have become national and even foreign problems can be reduced, resulted in the last 2 years the sky in Riau has turned blue due to a significant decrease in forest and land fires wherein 2019 there were 9,717.80 hectares of burned land and forest, reduced to 1,412.08 hectares in 2021.

Several roles performed by the personnel of Korem 031 Wira Bima in pre-disaster were routine patrols, aggressive patrols, and joint patrols involving other agencies at strong points of forest and land fires, doing real work by building ponds and water canals, conducting education tillage by not burning, maintaining good relations with the community people by sleeping and eating at people's homes. In the event of a fire, personnel extinguishes the fire immediately before it enlarges, if it cannot be controlled with the existing personnel, immediately report to the central task force to get assistance from the air task force to carry out water bombing and teknologi modifikasi cuaca (TMC)/ Weather Modification technology. At the time of post-fire, the role carried out was to help the affected community, especially the vulnerable, and immediately cooperate with the police to create a *police line* to evaluate the occurrence of fires.

The less than optimal role carried out by Korem 031/Wira Bima personnel during the Covid-19 pandemic was the result of the lack of personnel as a consequence of the deployment of troops in order to carry out other tasks, namely the success of the PSBB program and budget refocusing by the central government and regional governments as a result of the Covid-19 pandemic. Thus, the equipment for handling forest and land fires becomes inadequate.

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